

Achieving Medical Device EMC: The Role of Regulations, Standards, Guidelines and Publications

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Abstract: Many organizations around the world are currently working to improve EMC of electrical and electronic medical devices. Anecdotal evidence indicates that medical device manufacturers and healthcare providers are becoming increasingly knowledgeable and diligent regarding medical device EMI and EMC. Existing and new wireless services and other sources of EMD continue to proliferate; however at the same time, there is continuing development of regulations, standards, guidelines and publications that are intended to help prevent EMI and promote EMC and that can be applied to the safe use of RF sources and medical devices in hospitals. This paper provides a critical overview of the impact of such regulations, standards, guidelines and publications and their role in minimizing EMI malfunctions in healthcare. It also provides a bibliography that lists many of these important works.

INTRODUCTION

Considerable effort by many organizations around the world is currently devoted to improving the electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) of electrical and electronic medical devices. Existing and new wireless services and other sources of electromagnetic disturbance (EMD) continue to proliferate, e.g. existing and new wireless telephone services, digital television (DTV), wireless local area networks (LAN), "Bluetooth" equipment, and security systems. At the same time there is continuing development of regulations, standards, guidelines and publications that can be applied to the prevention of electromagnetic interference (EMI) and the promotion of EMC of electrical and electronic medical devices.

The current situation for medical device EMC in healthcare facilities is not ideal, but is improving. Healthcare organizations now have in their inventories and, due to financial constraints, will continue to use, older electrical and electronic medical devices that were not designed or tested for EMC. Such equipment is gradually being replaced with equipment for which the manufacturer claims compliance with current EMC standards. However, no EMC standard requires electronic medical equipment to be completely immune to every electromagnetic disturbance at any distance. Furthermore, compliance with EMC standards is usually demonstrated by type-testing, i.e. by testing only one prototype or a limited number of units. Performance of other units of the same model can differ. Also, electronic medical devices that would be totally immune to EMD would likely be too expensive or unusable (e.g. no displays or cables). Therefore, for the foreseeable future, healthcare organizations will need to manage EMC and the electromagnetic environment in their facilities. Ad hoc radiated RF immunity testing (e.g., [G3]) is a useful tool for assessing the effects of a particular RF source (e.g., a cellular telephone) on a particular medical device. This information can be applied to management of RF sources to assure their safe use in healthcare facilities, e.g. so that they are prohibited only in areas where such a prohibition is justified. Compliance by hospital staff, patients, and visitors with existing signage restricting such usage is difficult to enforce, and much of this signage has the limitation that it does not convey to staff, patients, and visitors that they should turn their cellular telephones off in restricted areas. As a

result, medical device EMI incidents caused by cellular telephones continue to be reported [P31]. Healthcare organizations should avail themselves of existing EMC/EMI information resources so that meaningful policies and procedures for managing the electromagnetic environment of electronic medical devices in healthcare facilities can be developed and implemented.

This paper will overview significant past, recent, and ongoing activity in the development of regulations, standards, guidelines and publications that have reduced the risk of EMI malfunctions and that have promoted medical device EMC in healthcare environments. Some of the major contributions are discussed in this paper, and many more are listed in the Bibliography.

REGULATIONS AND GUIDELINES

Many organizations have promulgated regulations and guidelines that have significantly impacted medical device EMC (e.g., European Union (EU) and member nations, the U.S. Federal Communications Commission (FCC), and the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (US FDA) Center for Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH). Industry Canada and the Medical Devices Bureau of Health Canada).

The regulatory activities that have had the greatest impact on medical device EMC are the European EMC Directive and the EMC requirements of the European Medical Device Directive. These are mandatory EMC requirements for medical devices intended for sale in Europe. The requirements led to significantly increased activity in EMC standards, much of which is still ongoing.

In the U.S., the FCC regulates licensed and unlicensed radio-frequency (RF) emitters. In response to industry assurances that electromagnetic emissions were not a problem for medical devices, it exempted most electrical and electronic medical devices from emissions requirements in 1980 [P45]. Regarding electromagnetic immunity, the FCC has the authority to regulate it only for home electronic equipment, and the FCC has chosen instead to encourage voluntary immunity standards for such equipment. Recently, the FCC promulgated regulations establishing a Wireless Medical Telemetry Service (WMTS). The importance of this cannot be overstated. For years, medical telemetry operated as a secondary user of the RF spectrum, and keeping a telemetry system working properly in these frequency bands in a healthcare facility could often be difficult. The FCC action [R3] was driven primarily by an EMI incident and the advocacy and hard work of the AHA/ASHE (see Table 2). The WMTS regulations specify RF spectrum in which medical telemetry is a primary user, and also make provisions for frequency coordination. Further information regarding wireless medical telemetry is presented by other authors in the current special session.

In the U.S., the Center for Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH) of the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) regulates the manufacture and sale of medical devices and electronic products that emit radiation. The regulations promulgated by the FDA/CDRH that have had the most significant impact on medical device EMC include

mandatory reporting by manufacturers and by user facilities of medical device problems [R4], "recognition" of voluntary consensus standards, and inclusion of design controls in the Quality System regulation [R5]. The first edition of IEC 60601-1-2 [S6] was "recognized" by FDA/CDRH in 1998. This enables manufacturers of applicable medical devices who reference the standard in their premarket submissions to the FDA to provide a declaration of conformity and summary information in lieu of a complete EMC test report. (Restrictions are listed under "Extent of Recognition" in the Supplementary Information document for the standard [W7].) Several recent CDRH medical device guidance documents reference IEC 60601-1-2.

STANDARDS AND GUIDELINES

The most significant standards activities pertaining to EMC of electrical and electronic medical devices have been conducted under the auspices of the organizations listed in Table 1. CDRH staff have made significant contributions in the development of medical device EMC standards and test methods.

Table 1: Organizations that have developed standards that have fostered EMC in healthcare (see Bibliography for selected individual references)

- American National Standards Institute Accredited Committee C63 (EMC)
- Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation (AAMI)
- Comité Européen Normalisation Electronique (CENELEC)
- Comité International Spécial Des Perturbations Radioélectriques (CISPR)
- International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)
- International Organization for Standardization (ISO)
- Rehabilitation Engineering Society of North America (RESNA)

Considerable effort has gone into the development of IEC and ISO standards applicable to medical devices and EMC. Most CENELEC standards (European Normes or ENs) that are applicable to medical device EMC are based on IEC standards. However, the mandatory nature of the EU directives and their implementation by the member nations has had the result that medical device manufacturers filing for clearance in the U.S. appear to be certifying compliance with the European Norms (ENs) more than any other standards.¹ For EMC of electrical and electronic medical devices, the EN equivalent of IEC 60601-1-2 appears to be cited most often.

IEC standard 60601-1-2 specifies EMC requirements and tests for medical electrical equipment. The first edition was published in 1993. The second edition has been under development since 1995, and publication is projected for mid-2001. The second edition is expected to have a significant impact on EMC of medical devices in healthcare facilities. In addition to specifying more stringent electromagnetic immunity requirements and additional tests, the second edition requires manufacturers to disclose much more information about the electromagnetic characteristics of their devices than most have in the past, including relatively detailed guidelines for management of the electromagnetic use environment of the product.

IEC 60601-1-2 is based on CISPR emissions standards and "Basic" EMC immunity standards developed by IEC Technical Committee (TC) 77, EMC. IEC standards generally can be categorized as one of the following types: Basic, Generic, Product Family, or Product. Basic standards specify test methods that can be referenced by the other types. Generic standards apply to products for which there is no product family or product standard. Product Family standards apply

to a group of equipment types sharing common characteristics, e.g. medical electrical equipment. Product standards apply to a particular type of equipment, e.g. electrocardiographs. The hierarchy of standards under the jurisdiction of TC 62, Electrical Equipment in Medical Practice, is shown in Figure 1. IEC 60601-1 [S4], the "parent standard," is a Product Family standard for medical electrical equipment. The Collateral Standards, IEC 60601-1-X, of which IEC 60601-1-2 is one, add requirements to IEC 60601-1 and also apply to the product family. The IEC 60601-2-X standards, known as "Particular" or "Part two" standards, are Product Standards, e.g. IEC 60601-2-25, Particular requirements for the safety of electrocardiographs. They supplement, and in some cases substitute for, requirements of the Product Family Standard. The IEC 60601-3-X standards, Product Standards for essential performance of particular types of medical electrical equipment, will likely be absorbed into the "Part two" standards when they are harmonized with the third edition of IEC 60601-1 [S5], which includes requirements for essential performance as well as safety.

Standards and guidelines developed by CDRH include MDS-201-0004 [G7] and the Reviewer Guidance for Premarket Notification Submissions, November 1993, Anesthesiology and Respiratory Devices Branch [G8]. For many years, MDS-201-0004 was used by some medical device manufacturers as a voluntary EMC standard. The quasi-static test specified for respiratory and anesthesiology devices in [G8] was developed by CDRH engineers. It is not duplicated in any other standard and is useful for testing immunity of high-gain circuits to movement of electrostatically charged objects and people.

Figure 1. The IEC 60601 family of standards

Technical Information Report (TIR) 18 [G1], developed by the AAMI EMC Committee, contains comprehensive recommendations and guidelines for management of EMC in healthcare facilities and provides a model policy for EMC management, with guidance in customizing the policy for an individual healthcare organization. It should have made a significant impact on medical device EMC; however, it has not been sufficiently well disseminated to have the intended effect.

Recommended practice ANSI C63.18 [G2] is increasingly being used for medical device ad hoc radiated RF immunity testing. It was inspired by the pioneering ad hoc testing described by M.L. Rice and J.M. Smith in "Study of Electromagnetic Interference Between Portable Cellular Phones and Medical Equipment," presented at the 1993 Canadian Medical and Biological Engineering Conference, and also by Tan [P43] and Segal [P62]. The C63.18 recommended practice contributed to prevention of patient injury when it was used to discover RF susceptibility of a defibrillator. C63.18 ad hoc testing revealed that unintended discharge could be caused by a paging

¹ Thanh Nguyen, FDA/CDRH, private communication, April 2000.

transmitter.² Furthermore, researchers are increasingly reporting that they are using C63.18 in their ad hoc testing ([P5], [P33], [P58], [P78]). It has even been used to test non-medical systems such as integrated circuit manufacturing equipment and milk pasteurization equipment.³

PUBLICATIONS

EMC education has been widely recognized as a highly effective means of fostering EMC in healthcare, and EMC publications are a cost-effective way of achieving EMC education. In addition to the standards, guidelines, and regulations already mentioned, many publications (see Table 2) have had a significant impact on medical device EMC. Such publications have also led to numerous other significant medical device EMC activities. While it is not possible to list them all, the high level of activity in medical device EMC is evidenced by the sampling that appears in the Bibliography.

A publication that can be expected to have a significant impact on medical device EMC in healthcare facilities is a Report of the American Medical Association (AMA) Council on Scientific Affairs [P49]. ([W2] is a summary of the report.) It contains recommendations from doctors to healthcare staff and administrators for achieving EMC in healthcare facilities, and also concurs with the recommendations of AAMI TIR-18 [G1] and the McGill Group on EMC [P66].

Table 2: Publications and organizations whose publications have fostered EMC in healthcare (see Bibliography for selected individual references)

AAMI/FDA conference proceedings
American Society for Healthcare Engineering (ASHE) of the American Hospital Association (AHA)
Biomedical Instrumentation & Technology (BIT), published by AAMI Compliance Engineering
The U.S. Federal Communications Commission
The U.S. FDA Center for Devices and Radiological Health
The U.S. FDA Winchester Engineering and Analytical Center (WEAC)
Health Canada Medical Devices Bureau
Health Devices, published by ECRI
IEEE EMC Symposium Proceedings
ITEM (The International Journal of EMC)
The Journal of Clinical Engineering
McGill Biomedical Engineering Group on EMC
Proceedings of the Round Table on EMC in Health Care (Ottawa, Ontario, Sept. 1994)
Proceedings of the Workshop, Electromagnetic Interference and EMC in Health Care Facilities (Edmonton, Alberta, 1987)
The University of Oklahoma Center for the Study of Wireless EMC

The Internet is an outstanding communication medium and it will have a great impact on medical device EMC. Healthcare organizations are encouraged to review the publications and guidance on the EMC web pages listed in the Bibliography.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Healthcare organizations should review and consider existing information resources on management of EMC in healthcare facilities, particularly the guidance provided by AAMI TIR-18 [G1], C63.18 [G2], the U.K. MDA [W8], ECRI [P20], and the AMA report on the use of wireless RF equipment [P49]. Once the second edition of IEC 60601-1-2 [S5] is in use, the EMC guidance it requires to be

supplied by medical device manufacturers with new medical electrical equipment should also be considered. Appropriate management of wireless RF sources and the EMC of all electrical equipment in healthcare facilities will help to achieve the convenience and productivity that wireless equipment can offer while assuring the safe use of electrical and electronic medical devices.

CONCLUSIONS

The contributions of only a few of the many organizations around the world that are currently working to prevent EMI and assure EMC of electrical and electronic medical devices through development of regulations, standards, guidelines and publications have been overviewed. The net impact of the proliferation of wireless equipment and services and the many ongoing medical device EMC activities is difficult to assess. Anecdotal evidence indicates that medical device manufacturers and healthcare providers are increasingly knowledgeable and diligent regarding medical device EMI and EMC. While the tremendous amount of activity in medical device EMC appears to have kept constant, or reduced, the occurrence of EMI problems, these problems have not been eliminated. There is more yet to be done. As always, manufacturers of electrical and electronic medical devices should continue working for lower electromagnetic emissions and higher immunity of their products. EMC engineers will play a key role in such activities. However, until all medical devices in use are immune to any expected electromagnetic disturbance at any distance, purchasers and users of electronic medical devices must continue to be vigilant regarding EMC and the electromagnetic use environment, to help prevent medical device EMI problems.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Guidelines

[G1] AAMI TIR No. 18-1997, Guidance on electromagnetic compatibility of medical devices for clinical/ biomedical engineers, Part 1: Radiated radio-frequency electromagnetic energy.

[G2] ANSI C63.18-1997, Recommended practice for an on-site, ad hoc test method for estimating radiated electromagnetic immunity of medical devices to specific radio-frequency transmitters. New York: ANSI, 1997.

[G3] *Electromagnetic Interference Management in the Hospital Environment, Part I: An Introduction*, EMC Report 1996-1, Apr. 1996, Center for the Study of Wireless Electromagnetic Compatibility, The University of Oklahoma.

[G4] IEC 61000-5-1 (1996-12), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)—Part 5: Installation and mitigation guidelines—Section 1: General considerations.

[G5] IEC 61000-5-2 (1997-11), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)—Part 5: Installation and mitigation guidelines—Section 2: Earthing and cabling.

[G6] IEC 61000-5-6 (presently IEC 77B/157/CD), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)—Part 5: Installation and mitigation guidelines—Section 6: Mitigation of external influences (1995-08).

[G7] MDS-201-0004: 1979, Electromagnetic Compatibility Standard for Medical Devices (FDA voluntary guideline).⁴

[G8] Reviewer Guidance for Premarket Notification Submissions, November 1993, Respiratory and Anesthesiology Devices Branch (an FDA guidance document).⁵

⁴ Available as Accession Number PB271635 from the National Technical Information Service, 5285 Port Royal Road, Springfield, VA 22161, USA.

⁵ Available as "Excerpts related to EMI from Nov. 1993 Anesthesiology and Respiratory Devices Branch" from the CDRH web site at <http://www.fda.gov/cdrh/ode/638.pdf>.

² Stephen Juett, Baylor University Medical Center, private communication, January 2000.

³ Joseph Morissey, Motorola, private communication, March 2001.

Publications

- [P1] Adler, D., Margulies, L., Mahler, Y., and Israeli, A., "Measurements of electromagnetic fields radiated from communication equipment and of environmental electromagnetic noise: Impact on the use of communication equipment within the hospital," *Biomedical Instrumentation & Technology (BIT)*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 581-590, Nov./Dec. 1998.
- [P2] Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation, *Electromagnetic compatibility for medical devices—Issues and solutions*, FDA/AAMI Conference Report, 1996.
- [P3] Baba, I., Furuhashi, H., Kano, T., Watanabe, S., Ito, T., Nojima, T., and Tsubota, S., "Experimental study of electromagnetic interference from cellular phones with electronic medical equipment," *J. Clin. Eng.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 122-134, Mar./Apr. 1998.
- [P4] Barbaro, V., et al., "Do European GSM mobile phones pose a potential risk to pacemaker patients?" *PACE*, vol. 18, no. 6, 1995, pp. 1218-1224.
- [P5] Barbaro, V., Bartolini, P., Benassi, M., Di Nallo, A. M., Reali, L., and Valsecchi, S., "Electromagnetic interference by GSM cellular phones and UHF radios with intensive-care and operating-room ventilators," *BIT*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 361-369, Sep./Oct. 2000.
- [P6] Bassen, H.I., Moore, H.J., and Ruggera, P.S., "Cellular phone interference testing of implantable cardiac defibrillators, in-vitro," *Circulation (suppl.)*, vol. 92, no. 8, Oct. 15, 1995, p. 3547.
- [P7] Boisvert P., et al., "Preliminary survey of the electromagnetic interference environment in hospitals," *Proceedings of the 1991 IEEE Int. Symp. on EMC* (Cherry Hill, New Jersey, August 1991), pp. 214-219.
- [P8] Boivin, W. S., Boyd, S. M., Coletta, J. N., and Neunaber, L. M., "Measurement of radiofrequency electromagnetic fields in and around ambulances," *BIT*, vol. 31, no.2, pp. 145-154, Mar./Apr. 1997.
- [P9] Boyd, S. M., Boivin, W. S., Coletta, J. N., Harris, C. D., and Neunaber, L. M., "Characterization of the electromagnetic (EM) fields in critical medical device environments," *BIT*, vol. 31, no.6, pp. 572-573, Nov./Dec. 1997.
- [P10] Boyd, S. M., Boivin, W. S., Coletta, J. N., Harris, C. D., and Neunaber, L. M., "Documenting radiated electromagnetic field strength in the hospital environment," *J. Clin. Eng.*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 124-132, Mar./Apr. 1999.
- [P11] Boyd, S. M., Boivin, W. S., Coletta, J. N., Hamilton, S. L., Kerr, L. M., and Kempa, K., "Measurement of the static magnetic field of magnetic resonance imaging systems for MR safety testing of implanted medical devices," *J. Clin. Eng.*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 320-327, Nov./Dec. 2000.
- [P12] Carr, J.J., and Brown, J.M., *Introduction to Biomedical Equipment Technology*, 2nd ed. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1993.
- [P13] Carrillo, R., et al., "Preliminary observations on cellular telephones and pacemakers," *PACE*, vol. 18, no. 4, 1995, p. 863.
- [P14] Casamento, J.P., "Characterizing electromagnetic fields of common electronic article surveillance systems," *Compliance Eng.*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp.42-52, Sep./Oct. 1999.
- [P15] Center for the Study of Wireless Electromagnetic Compatibility, *Electromagnetic Interference Management in the Hospital Environment, Part I: An Introduction*, EMC Report 1996-1. The University of Oklahoma, April 1996.
- [P16] David, Y., Bukhari, A.R.S., and Paperman, W.D., "Management of electromagnetic interference at a hospital," *J. Clin. Eng.*, vol. 25, no.2, pp. 95-103, Mar./Apr. 2000.
- [P17] Davis, D., Segal, B., and Pavlasek, T., "Can minimum separation criteria ensure electromagnetic compatibility in hospitals? An experimental study," *BIT*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 411-416, Sep./Oct. 1999.
- [P18] ECRI, Action items; Oximeters, *Health Device Alerts*, p. 3, Oct. 1993.
- [P19] ECRI, Guidance article: "Cellular telephones and radio transmitters—interference with clinical equipment," *Health Devices*, vol. 22, pp. 8-9, Aug.-Sept. 1993.
- [P20] ECRI, Guidance article: "Electromagnetic interference and medical devices—an update on the use of cellular telephones and radio transmitters in healthcare facilities," *Health Devices*, vol. 25, nos. 2-3, Feb.-Mar. 1996.
- [P21] ECRI, User experience network: "Minimizing electromagnetic interference between medical devices," *Health Devices*, vol. 29, no. 7-8, pp. 294-295, Jul.-Aug. 2000.
- [P22] *Electromagnetic compatibility, interference and immunity in equipment and systems*. Milan, Italy: McGraw-Hill, 1993.
- [P23] FDA Safety Alert, *Important information on anti-theft and metal detector systems and pacemakers, ICDs, and spinal cord stimulators*, Sep. 1998.
- [P24] Finnish Institute of Occupational Health. *Safe use of mobile phones in hospitals*. 2000.
- [P25] Foster, K.R., et al., "Radiofrequency field surveys in hospitals," *BIT*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 155-159, Mar./Apr. 1996.
- [P26] Frank, U.A., Londner, R.T., "The hospital electromagnetic interference environment," *J. of the Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 246-254, Aug. 1971.
- [P27] Grant, H., "Managing electromagnetic compatibility between wireless and medical devices," *Compliance Eng.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 36-44, May/Jun. 1999.
- [P28] Grant, F.H. and Schlegel, R.E., "Planar separation effects: Pacemakers and wireless phones," *Compliance Eng. 1999 Annual Reference Guide*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 223-224, 1999.
- [P29] Gubisch, R.W., "Meeting the requirements for medical equipment EMC: A test house perspective," *BIT*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 132-137, Mar./Apr. 1999.
- [P30] Hayes D.L., et al., "A clinical study to assess the potential for hand-held wireless phones to interfere with implanted pacemakers" (abstract). Presented at the annual meeting of the North American Society for Electrophysiology and Pacing, May 1996, Seattle, WA.
- [P31] Hahn, I.H., Schnadower, D., Dakin, R., Hoffman, R.S., and Nelson, L., "Cell phone causes acute epinephrine poisoning," *J. Toxicology - Clinical Toxicology*, 2000; 38 pp. 525-6.
- [P32] Hanada, E., Watanabe, Y., Antoku, Y., Kenjo, Y., Nutahara, H., and Nose, Y., "Hospital construction materials: Poor shielding capacity with respect to signals transmitted by mobile telephones," *BIT*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 489-496, Sep./Oct. 1998.
- [P33] Hanada, E., Antoku, Y., Tani, S., Kimura, M., Hasegawa, A., Urano, S., Ohe, K., Yamaki, M., and Nose, Y., "Electromagnetic interference on medical equipment by low-power mobile telecommunication systems," *IEEE Trans. Electromagn. Compat.*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 470-476, Nov. 2000.
- [P34] Harris, C., Boivin, W., Boyd, S., Kerr, L., Kempa, K., Aronow, S., "Electromagnetic field strength levels surrounding electronic article surveillance (EAS) systems," *Health Physics*, vol. 78, no. 1, pp. 21-27, Jan. 2000.
- [P35] Hoolihan, D.D., "Setting the standard for hearing aids and electromagnetic interference," *Medical Electronics Manufacturing*, pp. 97-106. Fall 2000.
- [P36] IEEE Committee on Man and Radiation (COMAR), "COMAR reports radiofrequency interference with medical devices: A technical information statement," *IEEE Eng. Med. and Biol.*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 111-114, May/Jun. 1998.
- [P37] Irmich, W.E. and Tobisch, R., "Mobile phones in hospitals," *BIT*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 28-34, Jan./Feb. 1999.
- [P38] Joyner, K.H., Anderson, V., and Wood, M.P., "Interference and energy deposition rates from digital mobile phones," *Bioelectromagn. Soc. 1994 International Conference Abstract Handbook*, pp. 67-68.
- [P39] Kerr, L. M., Boivin, W. S., Boyd, S. M., and Coletta, J. N., "Measurement of radiated electromagnetic field levels before and after a changeover to energy-efficient lighting," *BIT*, vol. 35, no. 2, Mar./Apr. 2001.

- [P40] Kimmel, W.D. and Gerke, D.D., *Electromagnetic Compatibility in Medical Equipment: A Guide for Designers and Installers*. New York: IEEE Press; Buffalo Grove, IL: Interpharm Press, Inc., 1995.
- [P41] Kimmel, W.D. and Gerke, D.D., "Electromagnetic interference in the hospital environment," *Med. Dev. & Diag. Ind.*, May 1995, pp. 97-101.
- [P42] Kimmel, W.D. and Gerke, D.D., "Medical EMC: Standards revisions and new technology make for a busy time," *Compliance Eng.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 46-53, May/June 1999.
- [P43] Kisilevich, D. and Tan, K.S., "Affects of EMI on Medical Devices – Inside the Hospital", *Proceedings of the Round Table on EMC in Health Care* (Ottawa, Ontario, Sept. 1994) Care Technology, Alberta, Canada, pp. 39-41, 1995.
- [P44] Knapp, J., "Perspectives from the telecommunications and power industries," *Electromagnetic Compatibility for Medical Devices: Issues and Solutions*, FDA/AAMI Conference Report, AAMI, 1996.
- [P45] Knickerbocker, G., "Overview of EMI in health care facilities," *Proceedings of the Workshop, Electromagnetic Interference and Electromagnetic Compatibility in Health Care Facilities*, Nov. 18 and 19, 1987, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada.
- [P46] Knudson, T., and Bulkeley, W.M., "Clutter on the airwaves can block workings of medical electronics," *Wall Street Journal*, pp. A1, A8, June 15, 1994.
- [P47] Kole, W., "Preliminary broadband survey of electric fields in hospitals," *Proceedings of the Round Table on EMC in Health Care* (Ottawa, Ontario, Sept. 1994) Care Technology, Alberta, Canada, pp. 39-41, 1995.
- [P48] Liu-Hinz, C., Segal, B., and Pavlasek, T., "Estimates of electromagnetic compatibility requirements in health care environments," *Proc. 1996 Symp. Antenna Tech. and Applied Electromagnetics*, pp. 437-441.
- [P49] Lyznicki, J.M., Altman, R.D., and Williams, M.A., "Report of the American Medical Association Council on Scientific Affairs and AMA recommendations to medical professional staff on the use of wireless radio-frequency equipment in hospitals," *BIT*, vol. 35, no. 3, May/June 2001.
- [P50] Miller, S., "Electrosurgical interference in medical device design," *Proc. 1995 Medical Design and Manufacturing West Conference* (Santa Monica, California, Jan. 1995) Canon Communications, pp. 107-6-107-14.
- [P51] Morrissey J.J., Swicord M.L., and Balzano Q., "Characterization of electromagnetic interference of medical devices in the hospital from cell phone signal emissions," *Health Phys.* (submitted).
- [P52] Morrisson, R., *Grounding and Shielding Techniques in Instrumentation*. New York: John Wiley and Sons, 1967.
- [P53] Nelson, R., Ji, H., "Electric field strengths created by electrosurgical units," *Proc. 1994 Int. Symp. on EMC* (Chicago, Illinois, Aug. 1994), pp. 366-370.
- [P54] Nelson, R., Ji, H., "Electric and magnetic fields created by electrosurgical units," *IEEE Trans. Electromagn. Compat.*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 55-64, Feb. 1999.
- [P55] Paperman, E. D., David, Y., and McKee, K. A., *Electromagnetic Interference: Causes and Concerns in the Health Care Environment*. Chicago: American Society for Hospital Engineering of the American Hospital Association, Healthcare Facilities no. 055110, Aug. 1994.
- [P56] Pressly N., "Review of MDR reports reinforces concern about EMI," *FDA User Facility Reporting*, Summer 1997.
- [P57] *Proceedings of the Health Canada Medical Devices Bureau Round-Table Discussion on Electromagnetic Compatibility in Health Care*. Ottawa, Canada, Sept. 22-23, 1994. Care Technology, Alberta, Canada.
- [P58] Rice, W.P. "2.4 GHz RF WLAN EMI in medical devices," *J. Clin. Eng.*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 260-264, Sep./Oct. 2000.
- [P59] Ruggera, P.S., and O'Bryan, E.R., "Studies of apnea monitor radiofrequency electromagnetic interference," *Proc. Annual Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. in Med. and Biol. Soc.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 1641-1643, 1991.
- [P60] Ruggera, P.S., and Witters, D.M., "In vitro testing of pacemakers for digital cellular phone electromagnetic interference," *Proc. 31st Annual Meeting and Exposition of the AAMI*, p. 92, 1996.
- [P61] Schlegel, R.E., Grant, H., Raman, S., and Reynolds, D., "Electromagnetic compatibility study of the in-vitro interaction of wireless phones with cardiac pacemakers," *BIT*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 581-590, Nov./Dec. 1998.
- [P62] Segal, B., "Sources and victims: The potential magnitude of the electromagnetic interference problem," *Electromagnetic Compatibility for Medical Devices: Issues and Solutions*, FDA/AAMI Conference Report, AAMI, 1996.
- [P63] Segal, B., ed., *Proceedings of a Workshop on Electromagnetics, Health Care and Health*, held in association with the 17th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society and the 21st Canadian Medical and Biological Engineering Conference, Montreal, Canada, Sept. 19-20, 1995.
- [P64] Segal, B., et al., "Electromagnetic environment in hospitals," *Proc. Round Table on EMC in Health Care* (Ottawa, Ontario, Sept. 1994) Care Technology, Alberta, Canada, pp. 33-37, 1995.
- [P65] Segal, B., Retfalvi, S., and Pavlasek, T., "Silent malfunction of a critical-care device caused by EMI," *BIT*, vol. 29, pp. 350-354, 1994.
- [P66] Segal, B., Retfalvi, S., Townsend, D., and Pavlasek, T., "Recommendations for electromagnetic compatibility in health care," *Proceedings of Canadian Medical & Biological Engineering Conference* vol. 22, pp. 22-23, 1996. (Also reproduced in *Compliance Engineering*, vol. 14, pp. 81-83, 1996 and in *Compliance Engineering 1997 Annual Reference Guide*, vol. 14, no 3, pp. A149-A153.)
- [P67] Silberberg, J.L., "Performance degradation of electronic medical devices due to electromagnetic interference," *Compliance Eng.*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 25-39, Fall 1993.
- [P68] Silberberg, J.L., "Medical device electromagnetic interference issues, problem reports, standards, and recommendations," *Proceedings of the Health Canada Medical Devices Bureau Round-Table Discussion on Electromagnetic Compatibility in Health Care*, Ottawa, Canada, September 22-23, 1994, pp. 11-20.
- [P69] Silberberg, J.L., "Regulatory issues for electromagnetic compatibility of medical devices," *Wireless Communications Forum*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 17-22, Dec. 1994.
- [P70] Silberberg, J.L., "Electronic Medical Devices and EMI," *Compliance Eng.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. D14-D21, Feb. 1996. ([P67], with editorial improvements)
- [P71] Silberberg, J.L., "What can/should we learn from reports of medical device electromagnetic interference?," *Compliance Eng.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 41-57, May/June 1996. (Reprinted from [P63].)
- [P72] Silberberg, J.L., "What can reports of medical device electromagnetic interference tell us?" *Compliance Eng. 1997 Annual Ref. Guide*, pp. D17-D23. ([P71], with editorial improvements)
- [P73] Silbert, P.L. et al., "Interference from cellular telephones in the electroencephalogram," *J. Polysomnographic Tech.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 20-22, December 1994.
- [P74] Smith, J.M., Unger, F.W., and Bolcon, L., "Electromagnetic interference: Strategies for management in the clinical environment," *Proceedings of a Workshop on Electromagnetics, Health Care and Health*, held in association with the 17th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society and the 21st Canadian Medical and Biological Engineering Conference. Montreal, Canada, Sept. 19-20, 1995, pp. 37-38.
- [P75] Soltis, J. A., "Architectural engineering in the commercial marketplace," *Compliance Eng.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 9-14, Summer 1993.
- [P76] Sykes, S., ed. *Electromagnetic Compatibility for Medical Devices: Issues and Solutions*, FDA/AAMI Conference Report, AAMI, 1996.

[P77] Tan, K.S. and Hinberg, I., "Effects of a wireless local area network (LAN) system, a telemetry system, and electrosurgical devices on medical devices in a hospital environment," *BIT*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 115-118, Mar./Apr. 2000.

[P78] Turcotte, J. and Witters, D.M., "A practical technique for assessing electromagnetic interference in the clinical setting: Ad hoc testing," *BIT*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 241-252, May/June. 1998.

[P79] U.K. Medical Devices Agency, "Electromagnetic compatibility of medical devices with mobile communications, Device Bulletin DB9702, Mar. 1997.

[P80] Violette, J.L.N., White, D.R.J., and Violette, M.F., *Electromagnetic Compatibility Handbook*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold Co., 1987.

[P81] Vlach, P., *Measurement, Prediction & Analysis of the Radio-frequency Electromagnetic Environment Outside and Inside of Hospitals*. M.Eng Thesis (Elec. Eng.), McGill University, 1994.

[P82] Vlach, P., et al., "The electromagnetic environment due to portable sources in a typical hospital room," *Proc. 1995 IEEE Eng. in Med. & Biol. 17th Annual Conf. & 21st Canadian Med. and Biol. Eng. Conf.*, Montreal, Quebec, Sept. 1995.

[P83] Vlach, P., et al., "The measured and predicted electromagnetic environment at urban hospitals," *Proc. 1995 IEEE Int. Symp. on EMC*, pp. 4-7, Atlanta, Georgia, Aug. 1995.

[P84] White, D.R.J., *EMC Handbook: Electromagnetic Interference and Compatibility*. Volumes 1-12. Gainesville, VA: Don White Consultants, 1971.

[P85] Witters D.M., "Medical devices and EMI: The FDA perspective," *ITEM Update 1995*, pp. 22-32.

[P86] Witters, D.M. and Silberberg, J.L., "Electromagnetic interference with medical devices: FDA concerns and approaches toward solutions," *JCAHO The Environment of Care Series, Managing Electromagnetic Interference*. 1997(2):11-18, 1997.

Regulations

[R1] EU EMC Directive

[R2] EU Medical Device Directive

[R3] FCC Report and Order to Amend Parts 2 and 95 of the Commission's Rules to Create a Wireless Medical Telemetry Service, Released June 12, 2000, ET Docket 99-255.

[R4] FDA Medical Device Reporting regulation, including User Facility Reporting, 21 CFR, Part 803.

[R5] FDA Design Controls section of Quality System regulation, 21 CFR, Part 820.

Standards

[S1] ANSI RESNA WC/Vol. 2-1998, Volume 2: Additional Requirements for Wheelchairs (including Scooters) with Electrical Systems.

[S2] CISPR 11 (1997), Limits and methods of measurement of electromagnetic disturbance characteristics of industrial, scientific, and medical (ISM) radio-frequency equipment. Amendment 1 (1999).

[S3] CISPR 22 (1997), Limits and methods of measurement of electromagnetic disturbance characteristics of information technology equipment. Amendment 1 (2000).

[S4] IEC 60601-1 (1988), Medical electrical equipment—Part 1: General requirements for safety. Amendment 1 (1991). Amendment 2 (1995).

[S5] IEC 60601-1 (200X), Medical electrical equipment – Part 1: General requirements for safety and essential performance.⁶

[S6] IEC 60601-1-2 (1993), Medical electrical equipment—Part 1: General requirements for safety—2. Collateral Standard: Electromagnetic compatibility—Requirements and tests.

⁶ In preparation. Presently IEC/62A/321/CD (2000-11).

[S7] IEC 60601-1-2 (2001), Medical electrical equipment—Part 1: General requirements for safety—2. Collateral Standard: Electromagnetic compatibility—Requirements and tests.⁷

[S8] IEC 61000-4-2 (1995), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4: Testing and measurement techniques – Section 2: Electrostatic discharge immunity test – Basic EMC Publication. Amendment 1 (1998). Amendment 2 (2000).

[S9] IEC 61000-4-3 (1995), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)—Part 4: Testing and measurement techniques—Section 3: Radiated, radio-frequency, electromagnetic field immunity test. Amendment 1 (1998). Amendment 2 (2000).

[S10] IEC 61000-4-4 (1995), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4: Testing and measurement techniques – Section 4: Electrical fast transient/burst immunity test – Basic EMC Publication. Amendment 1 (2000).

[S11] IEC 61000-4-5 (1995), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4: Testing and measurement techniques – Section 5: Surge immunity test. Amendment 1 (2000).

[S12] IEC 61000-4-6 (1996), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4: Testing and measurement techniques – Section 6: Immunity to conducted disturbances, induced by radio-frequency fields. Amendment 1 (2000).

[S13] IEC 61000-4-8 (1993), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4: Testing and measurement techniques – Section 8: Power frequency magnetic field immunity test – Basic EMC Publication. Amendment 1 (2000).

[S14] IEC 61000-4-11 (1994), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4: Testing and measuring techniques – Section 11: Voltage dips, short interruptions and voltage variations immunity tests. Amendment 1 (2000).

[S15] IEC 61000-6-1 (1997-07), Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 6: Generic standards – Section 1: Immunity for residential, commercial and light-industrial environments.

[S16] IEC 60050(161), International electrotechnical vocabulary – Chapter 161: Electromagnetic compatibility. Amendment 1 (1997). Amendment 2 (1998).

[S17] IEEE 473-1985, Environmental site survey (10 kHz to 10 GHz), New York, IEEE, 1985.

[S18] MIL-STD-461E, Requirements for the Control of Electromagnetic Interference Emissions and Susceptibility.⁸

[S19] MIL-STD-462E, Measurement of Electromagnetic Interference Characteristics.

Internet web pages

[W1] AAMI, <http://www.aami.org>

[W2] American Medical Association Council on Scientific Affairs, "Report 4: Use of wireless radio-frequency devices in hospitals," <http://www.ama-assn.org/ama/pub/article/2036-2918.html>

[W3] ANSI Accredited Committee C63, <http://c63.ieee.org/>

[W4] ECRI, <http://www.ecri.org>

[W5] FDA/CDRH EMC page, <http://www.fda.gov/cdrh/emc/>

[W6] FDA/CDRH Safety Alerts, Public Health Advisories, and Notices, <http://www.fda.gov/cdrh/safety.html>

[W7] FDA/CDRH, Supplementary Information to recognition of IEC 60601-1-2 (1993), http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/cdrh/cfdocs/cfStandards/Detail.CFM?STANDARD_IDENTIFICATION_NO=355

[W8] IEC, <http://www.iec.ch/>

[W9] UK Medical Devices Agency, "Mobile communications: Interference with medical devices during the millennium period," [http://www.medical-devices.gov.uk/sn1999\(39\).htm](http://www.medical-devices.gov.uk/sn1999(39).htm)

[W10] University of Oklahoma Center for the Study of Wireless EMC, <http://www.ou.edu/engineering/emc/>

⁷ In preparation. IEC 62A/308/CDV (2000-02) and its revision, IEC 62A/XXX/FDIS (number not known at the time of preparation of this paper).

⁸ MIL-STDs are available from Defense Printing Service Detachment Office, 700 Robbins Avenue, Philadelphia, PA 19111-5094, USA